

None of the insecticides retarded seedling growth at the tested doses. Chlorpyrifos, disulfoton, monocrotophos, endosulfan, and basudin favored seedling growth. Of the granular formulations, phorate at 12.5, 10.0, and 7.5 kg a.i./kg seed per hectare was effective against the pest both in initial and residual toxicities; it was closely followed by chlorfenvinphos and disulfoton at 12.5

kg a.i. Next in order of effectiveness were chlorfenvinphos and disulfoton at 10.0 kg a.i., fenthion at 12.5 and 10.0 kg a.i., and quinalphos and chlorpyrifos at 12.5 kg a.i. Among the foliar sprays, carbofuran at concentrations of 0.1% and 0.075% was superior. Monocrotophos was next in effectiveness.

It was concluded that a single application of phorate at 7.5 kg a.i./350

kg seed per hectare, applied along with rice seed, can keep it free of the adult *D. armigera* throughout the nursery period. Carbofuran at 0.1% is the choice among foliar sprays. The granules were tried at high levels to check for adverse effect on the seedlings. Very low levels of 1 to 1.5 kg ai. were also found effective.

Residues of phorate-gamma BHC and mephosfolan in Jaya grain and straw

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Granular insecticides, introduced on a large scale in India during 1967 and 1968 have become popular with Indian farmers. Following application, translocation may result in retention of small quantities of poisons or their metabolites in the plant tissue. In view of the possible health hazard, it is imperative to analyze quantitatively the residue to find out if it is below or above the tolerance limit.

Two recently introduced granular insecticides, phorate-gamma BHC — Paddigard 7.5 G, containing 5% phorate (thimet) plus 2.5% BHC — and

mephosfolan (Cytrolane 5 G), were tested during boro (summer season) to determine the residues in the grain and straw of Jaya.

Table 2. Cytrolane residue^a in Jaya rice grain and straw.

Treatment	Cytrolane (ppm)	
	Grain	Straw
Cytrolane 5 G 0.5 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT	0.03	0.13
Cytrolane 5 G 0.5 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.06	0.36
Cytrolane 5 G 1.0 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT	0.06	0.13
Cytrolane 5 G 1.0 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.04	0.28
Control	0.04	0.01

^aMean of 3 replicates.
DT = days after transplanting.

Table 1. Phorate and gamma BHC residues^a in Jaya rice grain and straw, Burdwan, India.

Treatment	Phorate (ppm)	Phorate oxygen analogue sulphone (ppm)	Phorate oxygen analogue (ppm)	Phorate sulphone (ppm)	Gamma BHC (ppm)
<i>Grain</i>					
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT ^b	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.02
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.02
Control (grain)	0.02	0.04	0.06	0.04	0.02
<i>Straw</i>					
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 55 DT	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.05	0.06
Paddigard 7.5 G 1.5 kg/ha at 25 and 70 DT	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.08	0.06
Control (straw)	0.02	0.05	0.06	0.04	0.06

^aMean of 3 replicates. ^bDT = days after transplanting.

Each of the seven treatments was replicated three times in the experimental plots in Burdwan, India. Impounded water was maintained at a depth of about 4 cm during the vegetative and reproductive phases. The soil was fine loamy (clay loam). After harvest, random samples of rice and straw were airshipped to the ACCO Product Development Laboratory, Europe-African Region, Gosport, England, for gas-liquid chromatographic assay. The results are summarized in Tables 1 and 2.

Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests

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The intensification of farming practices, deforestation, indiscriminate use of pesticides (especially broad-spectrum and persistent ones) and a consequent decline in population of natural enemies of insects, and other disrupting forces in the ecosystem have accentuated the problem of insect pests on rice, particularly in the warm and humid tropics. Generally the nontolerant high-yielding rice varieties (HYV) suffer most from insect damage, especially during kharif (wet season) when the main rice crop is grown. Low yield associated with the kharif crop may be one reason for limited use of HW during that season.

An "Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests," drawn up by the Indian Council of Agricultural Research, started to function during kharif 1975 in the pest-prone area of Pandua, Bengal. Its principal objectives are 1) to determine why only about 15

percent of farmers' fields carried HW during kharif, 2) to determine the constraints on the transfer of technology and the constraints the farmers face in efficient pest management, and 3) to study how the gap between the farmers' yield and that achieved at rice experimental stations can be minimized. The farmers are being trained and encouraged to adopt improved packages of practices; to integrate different methods of pest management such as nursery treatment, use of more or less specific pesticides (preferably granular formulations when the insect population is at the economic threshold), weed control, land tillering after harvest, close cutting of the crop, planting of resistant varieties, use of light traps for monitoring; and surveillance, crop rotation, and other relevant practices.

The Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests aims at an interdisciplinary attack on other farmers' problems as well as pest management.

Some insecticide schedules tested against the paddy ear-cutting caterpillar in rice

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Some insecticide schedules were tested in 4- x 3-m plots of Saket-4, a rice that matures in about 110 days, during the July–October 1975 season at the Regional Agricultural Testing and Demonstration Centre, Varanasi, India. Combinations of paddy-water application of carbofuran, mephospolan, phorate, and disulfoton granules, and foliar sprays of fenitrothion and Ambithion were tested. Larval counts were taken at 76 days after transplanting (DT) by checking 20 hills diagonally across each plot.

The poorest control (1.8 larvae/hill) was attained with one application of 1.2 kg a.i. disulfoton/ha at 25 DT. None of the granules or sprays provided adequate control when applied alone. Results indicated that granules should be applied in combination with foliar sprays up to 65 DT to control ear-cutting caterpillar on early maturing varieties.

Incidence of rice gall midge and its parasites in Karnataka, India

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The rice gall midge is endemic in coastal Karnataka State. During the last 3 years, its presence has also been noted in the interior. Incidence has been severe in the summer crop. In summer 1975, 49 slender-grain cultivars were planted in three replications. The growing season varied from 92 to 120 days. The percentage of hills showing galls varied from 16.6 to 70.3. The number of galls per square meter varied from 9.5 in IET 3368 to 65.5 in IET 3201. All cultivars were susceptible to attack.

From the gall midge affected plants collected in the field, the following parasites emerged in the laboratory:

Platygasteridae – *Platygaster* sp.
Eupelmidae – *Neanastatus grallarius* (Masi)

Eulophidae – *Tetrastichus* sp.

Braconidae – ? *Gyrocampa* sp.

Ichneumonidae – *Gelis areator* (Panzer)

Ceratopogonidae – Unidentified

Of the six, *Platygaster* sp. and *Neanastatus* sp. parasitized more than 50% of the larvae.

Occurrence of the American rice water weevil in Japan

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In May 1976, the rice water weevil *Lissorptus oryzophilus* Kuschel was found in two regions of Aichi prefecture. The reports were the first of the pest in Japan. Specimens were sent to Australia and identified by Dr. G. Kuschel.

In the region of Tokoname, the weevils occurred in paddy fields of 600 ha. Over 10 grubs per hill were found on rice roots in June; rice plants were severely injured. In the region of Koda cho, about 30 m away from Tokoname, about 130 ha were damaged by the weevil. It is supposed that the

insect immigrated with hay imported from America 1 or 2 years earlier. Since the male adults have never been found, the insects are considered a parthenogenetic strain.

Brown planthopper attack in East Godavari, A.P., India

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Of about 1 million ha of rabi 1976 paddy that was grown in nine blocks in East Godavari District, India, about 3,250 ha was severely infested by brown planthoppers (BHP) and an estimated 200 ha suffered hopperburn. Many other fields harbored 100 to 1,000 BHP per clump by early April. Yield loss appeared widespread. RP 4-14 and Jaya were extensively grown among high yielding varieties.

Some 8- to 16-ha farms that received only one application of granular carbofuran, 40 to 50 days after planting, were practically free of BHP, while much of the nearby area received repeated insecticidal sprays at intervals of 7 to 10 days from 10 to 15 days after planting and suffered severe infestations. A survey in early April revealed hectic dusting or spraying in affected fields at 3- to 4-day intervals. Spiders, beetles, and hymenopterous parasites were absent from such fields. Indiscriminate, repeated spraying beginning with the early crop stage may have been responsible for the unprecedented outbreak. Dense plantings (70 to 90 clumps/sq m), while affording a favorable microclimate for BHP buildup, rendered sprays ineffective. An integrated strategy for combating the menace was tested in kharif 1976. BHP-resistant, high yielding cultures like CR57-MR.1523 were grown without plant protection, or susceptible varieties were grown and the following treatments were applied: dipping seedling roots for 12 hours in 0.02% chlorpyrifos before transplanting, transplanting not more than 40 to 50 hills/sq m, and applying granular insecticides when necessary on the basis of economic thresholds.